

Limitations in Teaching Mathematics and Sciences: An Overview

C. Jhansi Devi

Lecturer in Mathematics, New Science College, Hyderabad.

Abstract

Knowledge explosion took place with the help of epistemological developments helped Philosophy in evolving separate domain of studies. This development helped different scientists in developing certain theories in their respective fields and provided a wide scope for future study on parallel to the scientific inventions. This created lot of curiosity in the scientific world in taking up new areas of studies in understanding the Nature and Development. However, this curiosity came across lot of hurdles in continuing when the advocacy of these subjects like Mathematics and Sciences faces certain limitations. This paper highlights the limitations in taking Mathematics and Sciences, which would help us in locating the systematic deficiencies and as well suggest certain solutions in overcoming those limitations.

Keywords: Teaching Community, Intellectual Capabilities, Paradoxical Contradiction, Experiential Learning, National Curriculum Forum, Faculty Development Programme, Deep thinking, Confidence, Courage, Comprehensive Learning.

Introduction

The present paper discusses the limitations prevailing in the field of teaching especially concerning mathematics and other sciences. There has been a general impression across the teaching community about pursuing mathematics, as a subject of importance; it requires intellectual capabilities embedded with the critical analytical process that drives an individual to keep himself according to the new research carried out from time to time.

In the Indian context, the encouragement provided by the policymakers in terms of funding, infrastructure, and personnel is less. It requires impetus in promoting professionalism as part of the political agenda. A serious lacuna from the perspective of teacher educators is creating hurdles as identified many shortfalls in policy making.

The context in which the paper raises certain pertinent issues concerning the persistent demand by the policy makers for teacher educators to achieve excellence in teaching without defining what it meant. The paradoxical contradiction is covered by teacher educators across the educational field who need to reconcile their potentialities and professional identity concerning the political agenda of the policymakers. With this background, a pilot study conducted by administering group discussions and surveys revealed certain importance. Some narratives have given a mind map for navigating the process of science education in engaging students. The data corroborated from the interviews projected an interpretative thematic approach in analyzing the impressions of the teachers on very central issues like confidence, knowledge, and supererogation would together create excellent teaching abilities for Mathematics and Science teachers.

The vital terms prompted by the discussion provided certain issues of excellence, and quality teaching, corresponding to the outcome through the performances manifested in the examinations by the students. Contradictory to the policy statement, demanded by the policymakers on excellence, without providing a proper interpretation of excellence. It also failed to provide certain measures for scaling excellence. With this background, excellence is a quality that puts the terms outstanding, extremely, and exceptional as prerequisites. By this, it pushes teachers about being better than good, without having professional perfection in engaging the knowledge attained in disseminating to the students. It gives us an impression from the concerns raised by the participants in the study like the one that a teacher deemed to be excellent in 1980 may not be assessed as excellent in 2013 and vice-versa. This is because pedagogical, and technological changes introduced not upgraded to the then excellent teacher for the reasons change happened in the technology-driven education pushed the teacher much behind the excellence. Perhaps, the policymakers might not have thought of upgrading the teachers from time to time in line with the changes that are taking place in the domain.

The focus of the inquiry in the study was to determine the understandings and beliefs through a variety of sources collected from the field from the participants who gave different experiences and expertise in mathematics and sciences. In analyzing data, the study used qualitative, interpretative, and paradigmatic methods processed by employing explorative and cultural knowledge skills, cognition and emotions contributed to their excellent identity (Yin 2009). It is assumed from the concerns of the group provided a serious lead for creative approaches in teaching not only to make learning more relevant rather enjoyable for the students by developing more interest in understanding the themes on a deeper level as it is judged as mathematics is being taught through meaningless activity. (Nooriafshar, 2004). This is related to performance when combined with teaching which recognizes the individual central and may vary during the lessons as well as in longer periods. (Lev-zaminleikin, 2011). One of the leading mathematicians Mason, (2012) proposed a very important method for the student learning process using a problem-solving approach through experiential learning, which not only improves students' mathematics skills but also develops the independence gained and further enhances their confidence.

Promoting Teacher Education: Professional Development

The prevalence of socio-economic disparities at home and the learning sphere need a serious attempt through teacher education, which is limiting the learning opportunities of the students, which is constitutionally guaranteed and endorsed by certain schemes introduced by the government. Given the scenario at all three levels of education concerning mathematics, the designed curriculum provides an environment by situating the learning of mathematics in a diverse context. This is a critical departure from the existing approach of basic school mathematics, which is highly dominant across the country and creates a certain amount of non-cognizable mentality in the students. This approach is slowly creating a considerable change in perceiving learning mathematics. Consequent to the changes observed in the mathematics teaching-learning processes, a few challenges are encountered in the arena of teachers' professional development programs which needs to understand and should introduce the required changes drawn from the classroom experiences. These are essential for a variety of

reasons such as standardizing learning processes and systematically practicing them. This calls for a change in the mindsets of the mathematics teacher about what constitutes the teaching of mathematics. A conventional understanding of trained and socialized teachers normally applies certain thumb rules while solving certain mathematical problems. This is a contrast to the suggestions made by National Curriculum Forum which suggested certain strategies be evolved from their own experiences gained from classroom teaching. which is two-fold in its nature, one is encouraging children to think and reason for the problems that are suggested. The other provides an opportunity for the teaching community to develop pedagogical knowledge, which suits the students. This strategy particularly would help students who come from rural areas and educationally backward communities, which do not have the opportunity of having access to quality education in mathematics and other science subjects.

It is also essential in terms of improvising the capabilities of teachers by enabling them to acquire the skills required to manage and transform the classroom space from passive listening to perspective learning, which slows down the authority of the mathematics teachers in the classroom.

The training offered through professional development programs is needed to be able to realize the goals of social justice and equity concerns in mathematics education by ensuring that female students who hail from rural, poor, tribal backgrounds and marginalized castes get the benefit of the sensitization offered in the training.

The professionalism advocated in terms of proficiency in subject matters must prepare the teacher in knowing the reality about the students beyond the classroom transaction and thus provide a deeper understanding of the social realities clubbed with knowledge and pedagogical content.

It derived from *Darling-Hammonds'* theoretical model, Bartell (2011) projects self, society, students, and school as four essential key factors that lead teachers in learning to teach for the cause of social justice. In a true sense, self includes reflection of teachers in the process of learning teachings, and how their beliefs are guided in understanding the learning processes of the children, which have a lot of influence on them in terms of the cultural, historical, and economic context in which they brought up. Society should realize that learning, teaching, and schooling need to be understood, as they are linked to economic, political, and social power structures. Third, students have to be viewed in non-stereotypical ways while acknowledging and understanding how socio-cultural context influences their lives and learning, which encompasses the overall evolution of their understanding of the subject. The fourth pillar that is the school needs to provide a platform for the students to develop and enact practices that provide psychological support to them. All these factors are very essential and each one of them is significant in its context. The major chunk of students come to the learning platforms with lots of deficiencies with deprivation of many issues like lack of quality teaching and lack of quality engagement in the learning process. This scenario is widely prevalent in the Indian context and needs to be strategized as teachers are preconditioned as they have very low expectations from the students as have deep sociological biases about these marginalized students.

Faculty Development Programme

Aspects of the long-term Faculty Development Programme facilitated the problems of poor and inconsistent Maths and Science subjects and knowledge and pedagogical issues which are more important for the improvement of teaching and would enhance teachers' confidence and attitude (Williams),2012.

FDP's role is to provide a wide range of opportunities for improving maths and science teaching with the process applied to generate a better understanding of the content (Tuners) and Mcculloch, 2004. The training also results in teachers' performance on a better scale with improved confidence, which would enable them to become a more effective teacher. A huge range of benefits in FIP provides a brand overview of certain concepts like "Deep thinking" "Confidence" and "Courage" according to Monei {2014}:78}. A teacher who has the head to work and thinks hard to overcome their lack of understanding and mathematical *self-esteem* often proves to be a more emphatic teacher than one who has rarely had to question their mathematical understanding.

A key feature of excellent teaching is confidence. It is believed that teaching choices made by the excellent teacher arise from justifiable (as opposed to deluded) confidence is pivotal when making decisions. It believes that the excellent teacher has confidence, with certainty to reach decisions that result in the best outcome in any circumstance or situation they encounter. Confidence permits the teacher to make mistakes, acknowledge if they do not know, know when pupil learning is good and when it is not (and what to do), be flexible, and creative and be prepared to take on challenges and risks. (Alexander (2004) respondent knowledge that lack of the necessary confidence in one can be improved by practice. Accepted that despite having the willingness to try, under-confidence may prevent even the cooperative teacher from succeeding.

Teacher confidence may be reflected in their attitude to challenge as a consequence, teachers from China were to be brought in for their "can-do attitude" to show English teachers how to have high expectations and support struggling children. Respondents when endeavouring to raise standards is the possibility that some teachers lack the confidence to be seen as fallible. The teacher may need to acknowledge that the child may be mathematically abler than they are.

Confidence was also discernible in the views of respondents from all four groups who recognized the need to be accountable, noting that all their teaching is done with an eye on the targets. The difficulty, the respondent acknowledged, is that they have to reconcile short-time and long-term targets and to achieve this, they need confidence, comparing the undoubted success of achieving the targets in a short time to the potential offered by taking an unknown amount of time with an outcome that may vary from the intention.

A short-term view could be considered as knowledge through content that is generally not embedded and so is transient, as identified by Skimp (1976). The excellent teacher has a long-term view of success for the child but needs to temper that with the need to achieve tangible, measurable results in the shorter term.

They would have preferred teachers and managers to have the confidence to set goals of knowledge through understanding or “comprehensive learning” (Romero & Mari, 2011:1), demonstrated through the application. Kolterman (1996) stated that for motivation that has intrinsic value, the goal is to ensure the best possible progress by the child. The need promoted by Alexander (2004) for the teacher to work with the natural learning instincts of the children, creating an education that pursues high – standards, and has more breadth and humanity than previously.

The discussions revealed that the excellence of a teacher is enhanced in an inclusive classroom. For example, the teacher should be able to listen to the children and know whether what they are saying is valid or not, including mistakes from which all can learn.

Common Trends in Mathematics Teacher Education

Students, researchers, faculty, teacher educators, and teacher trainers are considered lifelong learners, who engage themselves in research as well as theorizing some concepts of mathematics. Faculty are engaged in the active construction of knowledge embedded in a different context of social environment, which influence and shape them for better effective teaching. Faculty are expected to continuously update and reflect on their practice whenever it is needed.

Conclusion

Teacher education is pursued as a goal-directed intervention to enhance teachers' teaching and learning including all kinds of preparation.

Mathematics education sets a goal for the improvement of teacher knowledge and prepares them to become effective and improvise in terms of the cognitive growth of students. It is very difficult to find an answer to the question why? How and where? The mathematics teacher learns the important domains and specific knowledge of mathematics in a given passive environment as expressed by the group who participated in the study.

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